

Histopathological Pattern of Primary Ovarian Germ Cell Tumour in a Tertiary Care Centre from North East India: A Retrospective Study**Junu Devi¹, Manjula Choudhury², Valina Brahma³, Daljeet Kaur⁴, Jabin Musfique⁵, Azharul Islam Laskar⁶**¹Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam²Professor, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam⁵Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam, India⁶Post Graduate trainee, Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College, Guwahati, Assam, India

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Abstract**Introduction:** Primary ovarian germ cell tumors are rare and a heterogenous group of neoplasms with various histological pattern. It account for for 20% of all ovarian neoplasms and most commonly seen in young female and children and clinically presents with pain abdomen, abdominal lump. Benign ovarian germ cell tumors are more common than malignant tumors which accounts for about 2.5% of all ovarian malignancies.**Aim** of this study is to determine the clinical presentation of germ cell tumors of ovary in relation to age, parity, symptoms and evaluate the different histomorphological patterns and frequency of various germ cell tumors.**Materials and Methods:** It is a hospital based retrospective cross sectional study conducted for a period of one and half year in a tertiary care centre of north east India. Study data were retrieved from the histopathology section of Department of Pathology Gauhati medical college and Hospital. All the cases were rechecked and slides were reviewed systematically for histopathological diagnosis.**Results:** Most commonly affected age group is 26-45 year, mean age 32.8 years. Abdominal pain with lump was most common presentation. Six (18.75%) patients were nulliparous, 18(56.25%) parous and 8(25.0%) were unmarried girls. Out of 32 germ cell tumors 27(84.38%) were benign 5(15.62%) were malignant (P<0.002). Among the 32 germ cell benign cystic teratoma 27(84.38%) was the most common benign neoplasm and mixed germ cell tumor 2(6.25%) was the most common malignant neoplasm.**Conclusion:** Primary ovarian germ cell tumor are uncommon, most of the tumor seen in 26 to 45 years, malignant germ cell tumor are common in younger age group. Mature teratoma is most common benign tumor and mixed germ cell tumor is most common malignant tumor and surgery is the treatment of choice.**Keywords:** Germ cell tumor, Benign, malignant, teratoma, Dysgerminoma.

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Introduction

Germ cell tumours (GCTs) are a histologically diverse entity that can occur in a wide variety of locations and age groups [1]. The majority of GCTs have a gonadal origin and comprise a large portion of tumours of the testicles and ovaries, with a 95% and 30% prevalence of neoplasms in these organs, respectively. However a small numbers of germ cell tumours are found in extragonadal sites[2]. Approximately 25–30% of all ovarian tumours are of germ cell origin and of these 95% are benign and only 3–4% are malignant [3-6]. Eighty percent of malignant ovarian germ cell tumors are diagnosed before 30 yeares of age. Common cell of origin is Primordial germ cell [7].

Common presenting symptom is progressive abdominal pain with a palpable pelvic mass. Though ovarian germ cell tumors are common very less numbers of lituratures are there from north eastern region of India. Aim of this study is to evaluate the different histopathological pattern and frequency of germ cell tumours of ovary in north east India

Materials and Methods:

A hospital based retrospective cross sectional study was conducted for a period of one and half years from January 2022 to July 2023 in a tertiary care centre of north east India to determine the histopathological pattern of various germ cell

tumours of ovary with respect to age and clinical presentation of tumour and to calculate the prevalence of different germ cell tumours of ovary. Standard ethical practice was followed during the study. A total of 32 cases were analyzed. Clinical characteristics of patients and histopathological features of tumors were documented. All these study data were collected from histopathology section of the Department of Pathology, Gauhati Medical College & Hospital.

All the GCT ovary were analyzed with reference to age, gender, gross and histopathological features based on the data retrieved from histopathology register. All the slides of GCT ovary were reviewed systematically for histopathological diagnosis. All primary ovarian tumor with records were studied. Cases of germ cell tumors elsewhere in the body other than ovary and tumors of ovary other than germ cell tumors are excluded from the study.

All the slides of GCT ovary were reviewed systematically for histopathological diagnosis. Statistical analysis were done using MS excel spread sheet and statistical methods such as p value (<0.05) and Chi square comparisons to determine statistical significances were used.

Results

Total 32 cases of ovarian GCT were studied including clinical presentation and histopathological features. The age group varies from 5 to 70 years. The mean age of presentation was Majority of them were in the age group 26- 45 years (62.50%) followed. The most common clinical presentation was pain abdomen followed by lump abdomen 14(46.87%). Most of the patient were married 24(75%), 18(56%) multiparous, 6(18.75%) nulliparous and 8(25%) unmarried girl. Size of the ovarian tumor was less the 10 cm in 5(15.62%) cases, between 10-20 cm in 16(50%) cases and >20 cm in 11(34.37%) case. Out of 32 cases 27(84.37%) were benign neoplasms and 5(15.62%) were malignant (B: M=5.4:1). Benign tumors are common above 25 years and malignant tumors are common in <= 25 years. The histopathological subtypes of the tumors included 27 mature teratoma (84.38%), 2 mixed germ cell tumors (6.25%), Dysgerminoma (3.13%), yolk sac tumor (3.13%) and mature teratoma with malignant transformation (3.13%) one in each group.

Table 1: Clinical and histological features of the study population

Variables	Frequency
Mean age	32.8
Parity	
Nuliparous	6(18.75%)
Multiparous	18(56%)
Unmarried	8(25%)
Clinical presentation	
Pain abdomen	12(37.5%)
Pain abdomen+ lump	15(46.87%)
Lump	5(15.63%)
Tumor size	
< 10 cm	5(15.62%)
10-20 cm	16(50.0%)
>20 cm	11(34.37%)
Type of tumors	
Benign	27(84.37%)
Malignant	5(15.62%)
B:M	5.4:1
Histological type	
Mature teratoma	27(84.38%)
Mixed germ cell tumor	2(6.25%)
Dysgerminoma	1(3.13%)
Yolk sac tumor	1(3.13%)
Mature teratoma with malignant transformation	1(3.13%)

Table 2: Clinical presentation of GCT ovary with respect to age

Age Group (Years)	Number of Cases	Percentage
May-25	8	25%
26 - 45	20	62.50%
46 - 70	4	12.50%

Table 3: Clinical presentation of GCT ovary

Clinical Presentation	No. of Cases	Percentage
Pain abdomen	12	37.5
Pain abdomen followed by lump abdomen	15	46.87
Lump abdomen	5	15.63

Table 4: Distribution of benign and malignant GCT ovary with respect to age

Age Group	Benign	Malignant	Total
0-25	4	4	8
26-70	23	1	24

Benign: Malignant = 5.4

P < 0.002(chi sq value- 9.5605)

Table 5: Distribution of GCT ovary with respect to Histological subtypes.

Histological Type	No. of Cases	Percentage
Mature cystic teratoma	27	84.38%
Mixed GCT of ovary	2	6.25%
Yolk sac tumor	1	3.13%
Dysgerminoma	1	3.13%
Mature cystic teratoma with malignant transformation	1	3.13%

Figure 1: Bar diagram showing distribution of GCT ovary with respect to age. It was observed that most cases that is 20/32 cases (62.5%) are in the age group of 26-45 years.

Figure 2: Pie diagram showing clinical presentation of GCT of ovary.

Figure 3: Bar diagram showing distribution of benign and malignant GCT ovary with respect to age

Figure 4: Pie diagram showing distribution of GCT ovary with respect to histological subtypes

Figure 5: Gross appearance of mature cystic teratoma (A); Low power view of mature cystic teratoma(B)

Figure 6: H & E. Photomicrograph of yolk sac tumour showing Schiller Duval bodies. (A) Low power view. (B) High power view.

Figure 7: H & E. Photomicrograph of dysgerminoma showing sheets of tumor cells separated by fibrous bands with infiltration of lymphocytes. (A) low power view. (B) high power view

Figure 8: H & E, photomicrograph of mixed germ cell tumour (dysgerminoma + yolk sac tumor). (A) dysgerminoma, low power view. (B, C) YST, high power view. (C) showing Schiller Duval bodies

Figure 9: Gross picture of mature teratoma with solid area. Mature teratoma with squamous cell carcinoma.

Figure 10: (A) low power view, (B) high power view of mature teratoma. (C) low power view, (D) high power view of squamous cell carcinoma (H & E)

Discussion

Ovarian germ cell tumors (GCT) represents a histologically heterogeneous group of tumors. Diagnosis of ovarian germ cell neoplasms primarily depends on the histo-morphological examination which is still the gold standard. Clinical presenting parameters such as age, site and size have additional values for overall diagnosis and management⁸. Although it occurs in all age groups in the present study age range from 5-70 years age with majority of cases found in 26-45 years of age (62.5%). Malignant GCT are more common in younger age group (<25 years) whereas benign GCT are more common in older age group (>25 years). Findings of the present study are similar to the study done by Binamra et al⁹. In the present study the youngest patient was a 17 year old female and oldest patient was 68 years old, a case of mature teratoma with malignant transformation. Most of the GCT of ovary presented with pain followed by lump abdomen (46.87%). This corresponds to the previous studies in which most of the GCT presented with pain abdomen and pelvic mass⁹. In the present series majority of the GCT of ovary are benign (84.4%) and a small portion is malignant (15.6%). De Backer et al¹⁰ presented in their study that out of 69 cases of GCT of ovary 54 (78.26%) were benign whereas 15 (21.73%) were malignant with predominant symptoms of pain and an abdominal/pelvic mass. S. P. Sah et al² also highlighted in their study that out of 121 cases of germ cell tumors of ovary 113 (93.39%) cases were found to be benign and only eight (6.61%) cases were malignant. Benign cystic teratoma is found to be the most common GCT in ovary accounting for 84.38% cases which is similar to the study done by Sah et al². Most previous studies shown the most common histological type of malignant ovarian germ cell tumors as dysgerminoma and immature teratoma⁹. However in the present study among the malignant GCT, the most common is mixed germ cell tumor (6.25%).

Treatment of germ cell tumors of ovary is according to further need of patient like desire for future fertility and presence of concomitant pelvic pathology and the extent of the tumor¹¹⁻¹⁴.

Malignant ovarian germ cell tumors are potentially curable after fertility sparing surgeries followed by adjuvant therapy, with overall survival rate of at least 95% for stage I and 75% for higher stage of the disease⁹.

The limitations of the study were small sample size due to the rarity of the lesions and retrospective nature

Conclusion

Ovarian germ cell tumors are uncommon and majority are benign with highest numbers of

Mature cystic teratoma occur above 25 years of age. Malignant ovarian germ cell tumors are rare which is common in young age. Surgery is the treatment of choice.

References

1. Zynger DL, Everton MJ, Dimov ND, Chou PM, Yang XJ. Expression of glypican 3 in ovarian and extragonadal germ cell tumors. *Am J Clin Pathol* 2008;130(2):224-30.
2. Sah SP, Uprety D, Rani S. Germ cell tumors of the ovary: a clinicopathologic study of 121 cases from Nepal. *J Obstet Gynaecol Res* 2004;30(4):303-8.
3. Deka M, Saikia CJ, Bezbaruah R. Analysis of Germ Cell Tumors of Ovary in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Two-Year Retrospective Study. *Int J Sci Stud* 2016;4(1):173-7.
4. Sharma I, Chaliha T. Histopathological patterns of germ cell tumours of ovary in a tertiary level hospital. *Int J Pharm Sci Inventions* 2014;3(10):14-24.
5. Schneider DT, Calaminus G, Koch S, Teske C, Schmidt P, Haas RJ, Harms D, Göbel U. Epidemiologic analysis of 1,442 children and adolescents registered in the German germ cell tumor protocols. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2004;42(2):169-75.
6. Jha R, Karki S. Histological pattern of ovarian tumors and their age distribution. *Nepal Med Coll J* 2008;10(2):81-5.
7. Nogales FF, Dulcey I, Preda O. Germ cell tumors of the ovary: an update. *Arch Pathol Lab Med* 2014;138(3):351-62.
8. Sheikine Y, Genega E, Melamed J, Lee P, Reuter VE, Ye H. Molecular genetics of testicular germ cell tumors. *Am J Cancer Res* 2012;2(2):153-67.
9. Patterson DM, Murugaesu N, Holden L, Seckl MJ, Rustin GJ. A review of the close surveillance policy for stage I female germ cell tumors of the ovary and other sites. *Int J Gynecological Cancer* 2008;18(1):43-50.
10. Mehra P, Aditi S, Prasad K M, et al. (April 28, 2023) Histomorphological Analysis of Ovarian Neoplasms According to the 2020 WHO Classification of Ovarian Tumors: A Distribution Pattern in a Tertiary Care Center. *Cureus* 15(4): e38273.
11. Sigdel B, Keshav C, Kayastha S, Puzhakkal S, Shukur RA, Sreedhar A, Augustine T, Peter BC. Clinicopathological Pattern and Survival Outcome of Malignant Ovarian Germ Cell Tumors: A Retrospective Study. *Pan Asian J Obs Gyn.* 2019;2(2):65-70.
12. De Backer A, Madern GC, Oosterhuis JW, Hakvoort-Cammel FG, Hazebroek FW. Ovarian germ cell tumors in children: a clinical study of 66 patients. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2006;46(4):459-64.

13. 11. Kaatsch P, Häfner C, Calaminus G, Blettner M, Tulla M. Pediatric germ cell tumors from 1987 to 2011: incidence rates, time trends, and survival. *Pediatr* 2015;135(1):e136-43.
14. 12. Terenziani M, Bisogno G, Boldrini R, Cecchetto G, Conte M, Boschetti L, De Pasquale MD, Biondi D, Inserra A, Siracusa F, Basso ME. Malignant ovarian germ cell tumors in pediatric patients: The AIEOP (Associazione Italiana Ematologia Oncologia Pediatrica) study. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2017;64(11):e26568.
15. 13. Mondal SK, Banyopadhyay R, Nag DR, Roychowdhury S, Mondal PK, Sinha SK. Histologic pattern, bilaterality and clinical evaluation of 957 ovarian neoplasms: A 10-year study in a tertiary hospital of eastern India. *J Can Res Ther* 2011; 7:433-7.
16. 14. Cecchetto G. Gonadal germ cell tumors in children and adolescents. *J Indian Assoc Pediatr Surg* 2014; 19:189-94.
17. 14. De Backer A, Madern GC, Oosterhuis JW, Hakvoort-Cammel FG, Hazebroek FW. Ovarian germ cell tumors in children: a clinical study of 66 patients. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2006;46(4):459-64.